

**For more
citizen science**

with the social sciences
and humanities

coeso
connecting research and society

For more citizen science

with the social sciences and humanities

The mis **match**

“Citizen Science” is an umbrella term that describes scientific research carried out in cooperation between professional and non-professional researchers, where “scientific” means a method-guided generation of theoretical as well as application-oriented knowledge, and “cooperation” presupposes an active and deliberate contribution by all parties to the common research. Social sciences and humanities (SSH) disciplines have a long-standing tradition of participatory research practices corresponding to this definition; nonetheless, these contributions lack visibility and recognition, generating the perception of an under-representation of these disciplines within the citizen science field.

Since its introduction in the 90s, the term “citizen science” mostly spread within the natural sciences, while the social sciences and humanities researchers kept using their own disciplinary languages, such as “action research” or “public humanities” – declined then in public history, public archaeology, public anthropology, etc.. The newly coined terms of “citizen social science” or “citizen humanities” are currently gaining attention in the citizen science landscape.

As the term “citizen science”, together with the benefits of participatory practices, became well known

and encouraged, the existing participatory research practices in the SSH did not also receive the benefits – the praise, recognition and support for opening science to society. However, **SSH contributions to citizen science are numerous; they need to be fully recognized as legitimate and valuable research practices, and they need to be a visible part of the scholarly communication ecosystem.**

Both the fact that SSH researchers doing participatory research do not recognize themselves in citizen science, and the fact that the citizen science community is still mostly unaware of the SSH contribution, create a mismatch that holds back the full potential of citizen science across disciplines, and hinders potential collaborations, especially with the third sector. Explicitly acknowledging and valuing citizen science within the social sciences and humanities at all levels, including within policies, could encourage more researchers to identify themselves as citizen science practitioners. This recognition would also benefit the entire citizen science community, which is known for its diversity, inclusivity, and collaborative nature, involving participants from various backgrounds; and would benefit those stakeholders willing to make a difference for society through engaging with professional research.

For more citizen science

with the social sciences and humanities

Why it matters

The citizen science community can learn from, reuse, and be inspired by the time-tested participatory methodologies used within SSH research. Showcasing and recognizing the value of these diverse participatory research practices within and beyond the academic community will not only encourage researchers to share their approaches and methodologies, it will also stimulate more SSH citizen science by allowing practitioners to recognize their work as valuable to those beyond their specific community.

However, **advocating for the importance of social sciences and humanities citizen science is ineffective without efforts to increase its visibility.** This requires current research

infrastructures and services to effectively showcase this specific form of research. Still, adapting these infrastructures and services to take

into account SSH citizen science, and securing the necessary funding for it, is challenging without prior acknowledgment of its value. This creates a circular issue, emphasizing the need for structural changes in the research ecosystem and its monitoring activities. Such a change would create space and visibility for citizen science and participatory research practices also in social sciences and humanities.

In the last decade, policy measures have significantly enhanced the prominence and appreciation of citizen science, by **recognizing citizen science as a key component of open science.** If researchers in the SSH who use participatory research methods do not identify their work as “citizen science”, they may also not recognize the available support, especially funding calls, that they are eligible for. Additionally, by not taking part in the growing citizen science community,

they may be missing out on knowledge sharing opportunities, and thus not benefiting from exchanging best practices with an expanded practitioner circle.

The issue is mirrored for the citizen science community as a whole – it is not benefiting as much as it could from the SSH contribution to citizen science. This is the case not just for the researchers, but also for other actors, such as civil society organizations (CSOs), which are interested in engaging with citizen science activities. These groups could greatly benefit from the established traditions and methodologies that underpin participatory research in the social sciences and humanities. **Keeping the potential of SSH citizen science locked hinders innovation, especially social innovation, and prevents the third sector to be empowered with the knowledge and methodologies that SSH offers.**

For more citizen science

with the social sciences and humanities

For policy makers, SSH citizen science initiatives' results can provide for instance innovative deliberative processes or critical data for evidence-based policy making. The EU funded YouCount project is an example of how a coordinated citizen social science action that includes participatory approaches can provide evidence on a common societal challenge, like social inclusion of young people in Europe, thanks to a multi-case approach across different European countries. Additionally, the ten pilot projects carried out within the COESO framework showcase what small-scale, highly collaborative, locally grounded citizen science initiatives can achieve for diverse specific communities or engaged stakeholders. For citizens engaged in social sciences and humanities citizen science projects, participating in research on topics of their interest can also act as a means to promote high-quality discussions on social issues and as a means to support empowerment in their daily lives. It also brings the research closer to them, making it more transparent, and thus more trustworthy.

For all these reasons, **overcoming the mismatch between the long-standing tradition of SSH participatory practices and recognizing and supporting more SSH contributions to citizen science also needs support at the policy level**, in order to foster funding for both mission oriented and frontier research, as well as for innovation, that includes participation as an intrinsic component, rather than a “nice to have” add-on.

The following recommendations are based from the experience collected over the 36-month implementation of the COESO project, funded by the European Commission, and the development of the VERA platform (vera.operas-eu.org), designed to support small-scale participatory projects within the social sciences and the humanities disciplines.

For more citizen science

with the social sciences and humanities

Releasing the **full potential** of SSH citizen science

R/1 Make SSH citizen science **visible and findable**

Although there is a movement to mainstream citizen science within the research community, citizen science still mostly lingers in the peripheral vision of most researchers and research supporters. Current scholarly communication channels have not yet fully incorporated citizen science into their core values, holding hurdles for citizen science in general to expand, and especially for citizen science within the social sciences and humanities disciplines, which are perceived as less prevalent in the field.

Researchers, practitioners and supporters of SSH citizen science should be encouraged and supported to make their participatory practices more visible, thus increasing the overall visibility of SSH contributions to citizen science. **The European citizen science communities at international and local levels are open to all disciplines, and they need more representation from SSH participatory research practitioners.** This will encourage the larger citizen science community to become more aware of the diverse approaches used in the SSH and also acknowledge the long-standing tradition of participatory practices in the SSH. Both actions can support the transition to new terminology – such as “citizen social science” or “citizen humanities” - when appropriate.

For SSH citizen science to become more visible, not only do the practitioners need to be more involved with the various citizen science communities, but the way they communicate their research needs to be recognized and supported. SSH research, in general, and especially small-scale, local citizen science initiatives, utilize unconventional or non-digital

main → takeaways

- Encourage and support more SSH researchers to join the citizen science community
- Explicitly acknowledge the SSH discipline-specific citizen science terminology in communication actions
- Provide SSH CS practitioners with communication support for their initiatives
- Create databases and scholarly communication platforms that competently search and showcase multilingual SSH citizen science results

For more citizen science

with the social sciences and humanities

communication formats for their outputs and results – for example, informational booklets or games to engage children. Furthermore, these results are often made with and tailored to specific local communities, resulting in multi-authored materials produced in the community's language. Practitioners need support to produce results within these different types and scales of communication and dissemination frameworks. For example, this could take the form of editorial support for blogs, designated space in established newsletters, or adding “research notes” sections in scientific journals.

Additionally, taking full advantage of existing research communication channels will help with visibility. SSH citizen science practitioners should be encouraged to disseminate their experiences and results in open access diamond disciplinary journals, and SSH citizen science initiatives should be specifically highlighted in citizen science focused journals and communication spaces.

Both the traditional and the “alternative” outputs also need to be findable within the existing scholarly communication environments. This requires journals and other research communication platforms to **accommodate the sometimes unconventional, non-digital, multilingual, locally-targeted communication formats that are created through small-scale, local SSH citizen science initiatives**. Databases and discovery platforms should explore novel ways to gather them, offer automatic translation services, and support multilingual vocabularies and ontologies to ensure accessibility and relevance across different linguistic groups. Additionally, a system that allows for giving credit to the diverse types of possible contributors needs to be provided. For all this to happen, **SSH infrastructures and citizen science infrastructures should be encouraged and supported in collaborating for this aim**.

For more citizen science

with the social sciences and humanities

Releasing the **full potential** of SSH citizen science

R/2 Foster a coordinated ecosystem of services that **supports and values** SSH citizen science practices

Although services, like science shops, that support participatory research practices, including SSH practices, have existed in Europe for decades, those initiatives are also mainly in the research institutions' periphery, even though they are recognized for providing technical and ethical guidance, in addition to the networking activity to build tailored and effective partnerships. Not only traditional scholarly communication channels then, but also support services and the research evaluation schemes have not yet fully incorporated citizen science into their core values.

Research service providers and research evaluators are invited to discover the citizen science services and "Citizen Science Hubs" that are emerging within universities throughout Europe, reinforcing the already existing local services such as the sciences shops, and also encouraging more of them: research libraries are also organizing themselves to support citizen science activities.

Digital hubs also exist in Europe: they are open research platforms supporting networking and participatory practices with non-academic stakeholders, such as Eu-citizen.science, country-based citizen science platforms, and VERA, that specifically target SSH participatory research. Additional support to further enhance these platforms is necessary. These digital infrastructures should follow the principles of open infrastructures, including the involvement of concerned stakeholders and relevant communities in their governance everytime appropriate.

Any platform or hub, whether digital, physical, global or local, should tightly connect and network with each other, in order to offer the community opportunities for knowledge exchange about best

main → takeaways

- Enable knowledge exchange across physical and digital spaces to support SSH collaboration techniques across disciplines and professions
- Encourage and support open infrastructures for participatory practices
- Support mutual learning experiences between SSH citizen science service providers
- Consider citizen science practices in all disciplines within the current research assessment reform process

For more citizen science

with the social sciences and humanities

practices and support communication activities to give projects more visibility and tailored support.

Although the existing services are currently associated with one another through associations such as the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA), there is still much room to improve the capacity for them to pool their resources and become complementary – to create networking support for practitioners with similar interests (languages, data type, topic, methodologies, etc.), thus building communities of practices. Digital spaces have the potential to provide an infrastructure for information and resource sharing across physical spaces and digital spaces. **Public infrastructures should be designed to ingest and categorize citizen science content, and local support services should be ready to train practitioners on how to most efficiently make use of the existing infrastructure.** This can be accomplished, in part, through mutual learning exercises among the various citizen science service providers.

All this work does not go without adequate human resources. Central to the need for all citizen science support services, including digital platforms, is securing dedicated and consistent support staff, who are available long-term. This ensures that communities providing services and those receiving services stay connected, engaged, and build a comprehensive supportive ecosystem together.

Adequate recognition at the institutional level is also imperative. **Citizen science practices should be considered for all disciplines in the current research assessment reform process,** in order to give value to research that uses citizen science and participatory methods. It's essential that researchers are positively acknowledged for incorporating participatory research into their work. Given its collaborative and time-intensive nature, participatory research should not be viewed as an optional extra or a 'nice-to-have' element. When researchers engage in participatory techniques, it often means less time for other research activities. This reality must be recognized and adequately accounted for within the research evaluation system.

For more citizen science

with the social sciences and humanities

Releasing the **full potential** of SSH citizen science

R/3 **Value the diversity** of research-focused partnerships appropriate for non-profit and social economy

Citizen science in the social science and humanities is often more effective and efficient when done together with local associations or not-for-profit organizations and social enterprises, and it can lead to unexpected results that are mutually beneficial for all involved – the academic researchers, the non-academic practitioners, and the local communities who are directly affected by the issue under investigation. But the way partnerships are formed, and the mutual benefits aimed for are not as result-oriented compared to innovation-scheme partnerships between STEM academic disciplines and industry, where the industrial partner invests in research with the aim to develop and sell a profitable product.

Research performing organisations (RPOs) and civil society organisations (CSOs) should encourage small-scale and highly collaborative projects between SSH research and the third sector, positively valuing that the motivation for SSH academic partners and non-for-profit organizations to work together is usually not profit-oriented on either side, although the partnerships do and can contribute to a short-term and/or long-term positive economic and social impact through joint research and innovation activities. In order to reach CSOs and encourage them to join forces with SSH research, **it is important to share information with them about what citizen science can look like in the SSH disciplines, and what it can bring in terms of innovation, besides the central component of civic empowerment.** CSOs and policy makers need to acknowledge that innovative approaches and

main → takeaways

- Value and encourage small-scale projects that involve intense collaborations between SSH research and the third sector
- Encourage innovative approaches and outcomes by enabling process-oriented, and not only result-oriented collaborations
- Support training programs related to social sciences and humanities citizen science targeting CSOs
- Provide neutral spaces for knowledge exchange
- Encourage research performing organizations in doing more formal collaborative engagement with CSOs, including mutual learning experiences

For more citizen science

with the social sciences and humanities

outcomes can be enabled by process-oriented, and not only result/solution-oriented collaborations.

Preparing the ground for diverse collaborations can also be accomplished with communication campaigns through national and European citizen science associations, joint conferences between RPOs and CSOs, and especially through trainings about citizen science and participatory research at advanced SSH degree university programs, thus preparing current and future researchers to responsibly, ethically and efficiently include participatory research practices throughout their career.

Additionally, **the need for inclusive interfaces for participation in research, both digital and physical, is high.** Regarding the digital interfaces, they should take into account the existing working frameworks of the partners involved. Regarding the physical spaces, they should provide a neutral - safe - space for sharing and experimenting. Thus, besides the core training activities mentioned above, universities and research performing organizations should encourage more room for mutual learning experiences among researchers and practitioners, for lifelong learning and sharing respective expertise.

For more citizen science

with the social sciences and humanities

Wrap-up

The full potential of citizen science with and within the social sciences and humanities can be unlocked through appropriate recognition of the long-standing traditions of participatory practices in these disciplines. **Building a bridge between “mainstreamed” citizen science and SSH participatory research requires that SSH researchers join the citizen science community and that the citizen science community understands and embraces the reality of the diverse SSH participatory practices and their corresponding terminology.** Digital and physical hubs that adequately showcase and support SSH citizen science projects, as well as trainings and mutual learning opportunities are complementary actions facilitating this process.

Small-scale, local citizen science initiatives should be given specific attention, as they lack resources to appropriately document and communicate their

activities and need more tailored support. More generally, **scholarly communication platforms and other support services such as science shops and the emerging “citizen science hubs” should be supported to help spread information about the diversity and the multilingual nature of the output formats that characterize both the SSH and small-scale citizen science.** This can be achieved with appropriate funding and through enhancing the complementarity between these services - whether digital or physical - while continuing to support and encourage mutual learning frameworks between them.

Finally, partnerships with SSH researchers to build effective citizen science initiatives should be encouraged and supported among the third sector, especially among actors of the non-profit and social economy, in order to foster social innovation, along with encouraging process-oriented innovations.

To go further:

Smaniotto, Alessia. «Fostering Funding for Citizen Science in the Social Sciences and Humanities - Policy Brief #1 (COESO D.1.4)», COESO project deliverables, 30 June 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6794981>

Smaniotto, Alessia. «The Social Sciences and Humanities Contributions to Citizen Science. Insights from the COESO Project Journey (COESO D.7.6)», COESO project deliverables, 29 December 2023. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10372437>

Göbel, Claudia, Sylvi Mauermeister, et Justus Henke. «Citizen Social Science in Germany—Cooperation beyond Invited and Uninvited Participation». *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications* 9, no 1 (7 June 2022): 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-022-01198-1>

Mayer, Katja, et Stefanie Schuerz. «Citizen Social Science: a promising approach for more participation in knowledge production and decision making». Zenodo, 13 December 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433089>

Ridley, Julie, Ingar Brattbakk, György Pataki, Alexandra Czeglédi, Fortuna Procentese, Flora Gatti, et Reidun Norvoll. «D1.3 Methodological Framework for Data Collection and Analysis», 28 February 2022. <https://zenodo.org/record/6303118>

Salnikova, Asya, Eugenia Vilarchao, Adam Brandstetter-Kunc, et Ildiko Ipolyi. «D1.4: TIME4CS Statement to Encourage Institutional Changes to Promote Citizen Science», 30 November 2023. <https://zenodo.org/records/10201230>

For more citizen science

with the social sciences and humanities

Authors: Alessia Smaniotto (EHESS-OpenEdition), Kelly Achenbach (MWS)

Contributors: Katja Mayer (University of Vienna)

29th December, 2023

POLICY BRIEF #2 **For more citizen science with the social sciences and humanities**

Acknowledgements

This policy brief also draws from the information collected during the COESO pilots' implementation, the COESO mutual learning exercise activities, including the participatory conference "Connect.Collaborate.Create" (ccc.sciencesconf.org), held in Paris-Aubervillier on Oct. 19th-21st, 2023; and from the discussions and shared experiences during extended networking activities between January 2021 and December 2023, including in particular the SwafS projects meetings – now ECS monthly meetings, the ECSA Networks working group, and the diverse webinars and conferences that the European citizen science community tirelessly organizes and facilitates.

COESO project is
coordinated by:

L'ÉCOLE
DES HAUTES
ÉTUDES EN
**SCIENCES
SOCIALES**

 OpenEdition

and supported by:

OPERAS
open scholarly communication in the european
research area for social sciences and humanities

Follow us:

coeso.hypotheses.org

@coesoeu

COESO received funding from the Horizon2020 SwafS-27-2020
Grant Agreement No.101006325

The content of this publication can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Commission.